

State Estimation with 1-Bit Observations and Imperfect Models: Bussgang Meets Kalman in Neural Networks

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Abstract—State estimation from noisy observations is a fundamental problem in many applications of signal processing. Traditional methods, such as the extended Kalman filter, work well under fully-known Gaussian models, while recent hybrid deep learning frameworks, combining model-based and data-driven approaches, can also handle partially known models and non-Gaussian noise. However, existing studies commonly assume the absence of quantization distortion, which is inevitable, especially with non-ideal analog-to-digital converters. In this work, we consider a state estimation problem with 1-bit quantization. 1-bit quantization causes significant quantization distortion and severe information loss, rendering conventional state estimation strategies unsuitable. To address this, inspired by the Bussgang decomposition technique, we first develop the Bussgang-aided Kalman filter by assuming perfectly known models. The proposed method suitably captures quantization distortion into the state estimation process. In addition, we propose a computationally efficient variant, referred to as the reduced Bussgang-aided Kalman filter and, building upon it, introduce a deep learning-based approach for handling partially known models, termed the Bussgang-aided KalmanNet. In particular, the Bussgang-aided KalmanNet jointly uses a dithering technique and a gated recurrent unit (GRU) architecture to effectively mitigate the effects of 1-bit quantization and model mismatch. Through simulations on the Lorenz-Attractor model and the Michigan NCLT dataset, we demonstrate that our proposed methods achieve accurate state estimation performance even under highly nonlinear, mismatched models and 1-bit observations.

Index Terms—State estimation, Kalman filter, Bussgang theorem, recurrent neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

State estimation serves as a fundamental pillar in numerous engineering applications, driving advancements in robotics, control systems, and signal processing. Formally, state estimation refers to estimating the internal states of a dynamic system using a set of observations, which may be incomplete, noisy, or otherwise imperfect. One celebrated approach to address the state estimation problem is the Kalman filter (KF) [1], [2]. In

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KF, the system’s hidden state is estimated recursively using a two-step process: prediction and update. During the prediction step, the filter forecasts the next state based on the system dynamics, incorporating prior knowledge and possible control inputs. In the update step, the filter corrects the estimate by incorporating the information from new observations while adjusting for uncertainties. Fundamentally, KF is another form of recursive linear minimum mean squared error (LMMSE) estimator, providing optimal estimates in terms of mean squared error (MSE) under the assumptions of Gaussian noise and linear system models.

Despite its efficiency, KF relies on certain idealized assumptions, such as linear system dynamics and Gaussian noise distributions. To address this, extensions of KF, including the extended Kalman filter (EKF) [3], [4] and the unscented Kalman filter (UKF) [5], were studied. A core idea of these variants is approximating non-Gaussian uncertainties as Gaussian distributions. For instance, EKF linearizes the system dynamics around the current estimate using a first-order Taylor expansion, thereby preserving the Gaussianity of the state distribution. Nonetheless, both the EKF and the UKF still depend on accurate knowledge of the system models, including the noise statistics and the system dynamics. However, in many real-world scenarios, these system models are only partially known and are often subject to non-Gaussian uncertainties [6], making these assumptions unrealistic.

Recently, to address the challenge posed by imperfect model knowledge, data-driven approaches have been extensively explored. In [7], recurrent Kalman network (RKN) was proposed, wherein a deep neural network (DNN) was directly used to mimic the prediction and update steps of EKF. In [8], a hybrid approach called KalmanNet was introduced that leverages DNNs to extract latent representations from data, even in the absence of an explicit system model. KalmanNet [8] is distinguished from RKN [7] in that a DNN does not completely replace the whole EKF process. Instead, it focuses solely on learning the Kalman gain, which is then integrated into the standard EKF process. Notably, [8] demonstrated that KalmanNet outperforms the EKF in the presence of model mismatch. Later, [9] developed Split-KalmanNet, whose core idea is separately learning the error covariance for the state and observation spaces to compute the Kalman gain. This separation enables more stable learning, particularly in highly nonlinear environments.

In addition to [9], numerous extensions of KalmanNet [8] have been actively investigated recently. Latent KalmanNet

[10] integrated a DNN-based encoder into KalmanNet, effectively transforming high-dimensional observations into a low-dimensional latent space. Cholesky-KalmanNet, proposed by [11], explicitly incorporated the positive-definite property of the covariance matrix through Cholesky decomposition, simultaneously enhancing explainability and estimation performance. In [12], Kalmanformer was proposed, which introduced the Transformer architecture into the Kalman gain learning process. [13] introduced explainable gated Bayesian recurrent neural network (EGBRNN), which addressed filtering limitations in non-Markovian systems by employing a DNN-based memory structure.

Notwithstanding the prior work, a critical yet underexplored aspect is the non-ideal nature of observation signals. In practice, measurements are often affected by noise, quantization errors, or hardware constraints, which can significantly impact the accuracy of state estimation. One particularly challenging case arises when considering 1-bit observations, where only binary information is available. This extreme quantization leads to substantial information loss, hindering accurate state estimation. Crucially, the existing state estimation techniques, including classical model-driven methods (such as EKF and UKF) as well as recent data-driven methods (such as KalmanNet), may struggle to perform reliably under such conditions, as they typically assume ideal observation data that does not account for quantization distortion. Accordingly, state estimation with 1-bit observations calls for tailored approaches capable of effectively extracting meaningful information from heavily quantized measurements.

In a different line of research, particularly in the literature on multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) communications, low-resolution quantizers have garnered significant attention within the context of energy-efficient communications. In [14], [15], quantizer selection methods for maximizing spectral efficiency or energy efficiency were developed, considering heterogeneous resolution quantizers. In [16], MIMO beamforming optimization was studied by employing non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA). In [17], the MIMO capacity with 1-bit quantizers was found by assuming perfect channel state information (CSI), while [18] characterized asymptotics for the MIMO mutual information when instantaneous CSI is not available. For uplink 1-bit MIMO systems, near-maximum-likelihood symbol detection methods were proposed in [19], [20]. In terms of handling the nonlinearity caused by 1-bit quantization, a popular approach is the Bussgang theorem [21]. In the context of channel estimation, for example, [22] proposed a Bussgang linear minimum mean squared error (BLMMSE) algorithm, which was later generalized in [23], [24], while [25] proposed an uplink pilot design using this technique. Indeed, the Bussgang theorem has been a valuable tool for various nonlinear systems, including considerations for state estimation [26]. However, these prior studies typically focus on specific communication problems with known system models. To the best of our knowledge, the state estimation problem with 1-bit quantization remains largely unexplored, and this work aims to fill this critical gap.

In this paper, we consider a state estimation problem where the observations are given as 1-bit quantized signals. To

logically develop our solution, we assume two main scenarios: 1) a perfectly known system dynamics model; 2) a partially known system dynamics model. For the case of known system models, we propose an efficient state estimation strategy called Bussgang-aided Kalman filter (BKF). A fundamental challenge in state estimation under 1-bit quantized observations stems from the highly nonlinear distortion induced by the coarse quantization of the measurements. To address this, BKF applies the Bussgang decomposition [21], [22], which approximates the highly nonlinear observations with a statistically equivalent linear representation, thereby enabling a tractable recursive state estimation process. To further mitigate the severe information loss caused by coarse quantization, we incorporate an adaptive dithering technique that shifts the decision threshold based on prior predictions. For improved efficiency, we also design rBKF, which approximates the filtering updates with substantially lower complexity while preserving estimation accuracy.

Subsequently, for partially known system models, we introduce Bussgang-aided KalmanNet (BKNet), a DNN-aided state estimation method. Based on the proposed rBKF structure, BKNet employs a hybrid design where only the Bussgang gain is learned by a DNN, while retaining rBKF's overall recursive estimation process. Specifically, BKNet employs DNNs composed of sequentially connected gated recurrent units (GRUs) modules, which effectively capture the error covariance terms associated with the Bussgang gain. Building upon this structure, the DNN is trained in a supervised manner, minimizing the MSE between the state estimates and the corresponding ground-truth states.

The design philosophy of the proposed BKNet adheres to that of KalmanNet [8]. This principle is known as model-based deep learning [27], which integrates domain knowledge into neural architectures to improve generalization and efficiency. Nonetheless, the conventional KalmanNet is not tailored to handle severely quantized observations. Therefore, its performance degrades significantly under 1-bit quantized observations. In contrast, our proposed BKNet explicitly incorporates the nonlinear effects of coarse quantization into its architecture, enabling robust state estimation. This constitutes a key novelty and a core technical contribution of our work.

In the numerical experiments, we demonstrate that the proposed methods perform effectively on the Lorenz attractor and Michigan NCLT dataset [28]. Under 1-bit observation conditions, BKF and BKNet achieve performance comparable to or exceeding that of EKF and KalmanNet under ideal observations, especially as the number of ADCs increases. Notably, BKNet exhibits robust performance under model mismatch conditions. It is also shown that rBKF significantly reduces inference time with minimal performance degradation. These results indicate that the challenges imposed by 1-bit quantized observations can be overcome through the proposed methods.

We summarize our contributions as follows.

- **State estimation with 1-bit observations:** We formulate a state estimation problem based on severely distorted 1-bit observations. The existing methods, including EKF and KalmanNet, are not suitable to address this problem

since they cannot handle the pronounced nonlinearity caused by the 1-bit quantizer.

- **BKF**: To address the problem for fully known system models, we propose two methods: BKF, a novel state estimation method that leverages the Bussgang decomposition and dithering, and its computationally efficient variant, rBKF. Our experiments show that the proposed methods achieve performance comparable to approaches based on ideal observation.
- **BKNet**: We also propose BKNet, a novel DNN-based state estimator based on rBKF, for scenarios involving 1-bit observations and partially known system models. BKNet achieves robust estimation performance even under 1-bit quantization, model mismatch, and non-Gaussian noise conditions.

Notations: Boldface uppercase and lowercase letters denote matrices and vectors (e.g., \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{a}), respectively. $\mathbf{A}[i, j]$ denotes the (i, j) -th entry of \mathbf{A} . \mathbf{I}_N denotes the $N \times N$ identity matrix. $\mathbf{1}_N$ denotes the $N \times 1$ vector whose elements are all equal to one. Superscripts $(\cdot)^\top$ and $(\cdot)^{-1}$ denote transpose and inversion. The operator $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ creates a diagonal matrix from a vector or extracts diagonal entries from a matrix. \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{N} denote the real numbers and natural numbers, respectively. The Gaussian distribution with mean μ and covariance Σ is denoted as $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$. The subscript notation $(\cdot)_t$ denotes data at time t , while $(\cdot)_{t|t-1}$ and $(\cdot)_{t|t}$ denote, respectively, the prediction and the estimate at time t based on observations up to time $t-1$ and t .

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we explain the considered system model for state estimation. For ease of exposition, we first assume ideal observation that does not incur any quantization distortion. Subsequently, we formulate the state estimation problem by incorporating 1-bit quantized observations.

A. Preliminaries: State Estimation with Ideal Observation

A conventional state estimation problem generally considers a discrete-time nonlinear state-space (SS) model with ideal observations. In this model, the overall state dynamics are fully described by a nonlinear function $\mathbf{f} : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ and a state uncertainty vector $\mathbf{w}_t \in \mathbb{R}^m$, namely,

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{t-1}) + \mathbf{w}_t. \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the observation model is also given by a nonlinear function $\mathbf{h} : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and an observation noise vector $\mathbf{v}_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}_t. \quad (2)$$

Typically, for modeling convenience, \mathbf{w}_t and \mathbf{v}_t are assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and covariances \mathbf{Q}_t and \mathbf{R}_t , i.e., $\mathbf{w}_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q}_t)$ and $\mathbf{v}_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{R}_t)$. As observed in (1) and (2), the observation \mathbf{y}_t depends only on the current state \mathbf{x}_t , and the current state \mathbf{x}_t depends only on the previous state \mathbf{x}_{t-1} , meaning that this SS model satisfies the Markov condition. Based on this, we formulate a state

estimation problem, which sequentially solves the following optimization:

$$\underset{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t}{\text{minimize}} \quad \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_t\|^2 | \mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_t]. \quad (3)$$

Under the Markov condition, EKF is a well-established and popular algorithm for effectively solving the state estimation problem in (3), as described in [3], [4]. Generally, EKF consists of two main steps: the prediction step and the update step. We explain these as follows.

- 1) **Prediction step:** In the prediction step, we obtain the prior mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$ of the state at time t , along with the corresponding prior error covariance $\Sigma_{t|t-1} = \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1})(\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1})^\top]$. For given posterior mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-1}$ and posterior error covariance $\Sigma_{t-1|t-1}$ updated at the previous time step, we predict $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$ and $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-1}), \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{F}_t \Sigma_{t-1|t-1} \mathbf{F}_t^\top + \mathbf{Q}_t, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{F}_t is the Jacobian of $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$ evaluated at $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$. Similarly, the prior observation mean $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}$ and its corresponding prior error covariance $\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1}$ are obtained by

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}), \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{H}_t \Sigma_{t|t-1} \mathbf{H}_t^\top + \mathbf{R}_t, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{H}_t is the Jacobian of $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$ evaluated at $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$.

- 2) **Update step:** After the prediction step, the predicted mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$ is updated by following

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{G}_t(\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}), \quad (8)$$

$$\Sigma_{t|t} = \Sigma_{t|t-1} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{G}_t \mathbf{P}_{t|t-1} \mathbf{K}\mathbf{G}_t^\top. \quad (9)$$

Here, the Kalman gain $\mathbf{K}\mathbf{G}_t$ adjusts the prior predicted mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$ using the observation \mathbf{y}_t and its predicted value $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}$. The Kalman gain is derived as

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{G}_t = \Sigma_{t|t-1} \mathbf{H}_t^\top \mathbf{P}_{t|t-1}^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

If \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{h} are linear functions, EKF reduces to conventional KF, achieving optimal performance in terms of MSE. Even in the presence of nonlinearities, EKF demonstrates high accuracy, provided that the statistical characteristics of \mathbf{w}_t and \mathbf{v}_t are fully known. However, in most real-world systems, neither the state uncertainty \mathbf{w}_t nor the noise \mathbf{v}_t characteristics are precisely known, and are typically non-Gaussian. To address these challenges, new state estimation methods leveraging DNNs have been investigated. Representative examples include KalmanNet [8] and Split-KalmanNet [9]. Specifically, KalmanNet is a hybrid architecture that combines the mathematical logic flow of EKF with the black-box characteristics of DNNs. In KalmanNet, a DNN learns the Kalman gain $\mathbf{K}\mathbf{G}_t$, effectively encoding noise information and providing an expressive yet interpretable solution that compensates for unknown system characteristics. Correspondingly, KalmanNet updates the state estimates as

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} + \mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)(\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}), \quad (11)$$

where $\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)$ is the learned Kalman gain, and Θ denotes trainable parameters optimized to minimize the MSE.

Fig. 1. Overall system structures for (a) ideal and (b) 1-bit observation environments.

We note that EKF and KalmanNet commonly assume ideal observations, meaning that the observation \mathbf{y}_t is obtained without any distortion other than observation noise \mathbf{v}_t . This system is simply illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

B. State Estimation with 1-Bit Observation

We now describe the state estimation problem with 1-bit observations, which is the primary focus of this paper. To represent the 1-bit quantized observation vector \mathbf{y}_t , we introduce \mathbf{r}_t , given by:

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y}_t), \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a element-wise 1-bit quantization function that returns

$$\mathbf{r}_t[i] = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y}_t[i]) = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{y}_t[i] > 0, \\ -1, & \mathbf{y}_t[i] \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

In particular, (13) indicates the zero-threshold ADC case. For clarity of notation, we hereafter denote the signal before the quantization operator $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$, i.e., \mathbf{y}_t , as the measurement model, and the quantized signal \mathbf{r}_t as the observation model.

Upon this, the state estimation problem is formulated as

$$\text{minimize } \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_t\|^2 | \mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_t]. \quad (14)$$

It is important to note that conventional methods such as EKF and KalmanNet cannot be directly applied to solve (14). This limitation mainly stems from the fact that these conventional methods inherently rely on a linear observation model, yet this is profoundly violated in (13) due to the highly nonlinear nature of 1-bit quantization $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$.

Remark 1 (Practical observation modeling). Our signal model assumes that the state variables are directly quantized. In practice, however, the states are not directly observable; instead, the system observes raw echoes that must be further processed to yield state-related measurements. In this regard, our setup may be considered idealized. Nevertheless, the contribution of our work remains significant: we propose a novel framework that enables state estimation under extreme quantization and also limited model knowledge, wherein conventional methods such as EKF and KalmanNet completely break down, as demonstrated later in our experiments. Our approach serves as a foundational framework upon which more advanced end-to-end solutions can be developed in future research. Furthermore, we emphasize that in certain scenarios, our model can be applied directly. For example, in frequency-modulated continuous wave (FMCW) radar systems, analog front-end components (e.g., phase-locked loops or phase detectors) can

extract stable voltage signals from the raw echoes that are proportional to range and velocity. These processed signals naturally serve as suitable measurements for BKF and BKNet, thereby enabling the construction of an effective state-space model and the successful application of our methodology.

III. BUSSGANG-AIDED KALMAN FILTER

In this section, to establish a theoretical foundation for solving (14), we first propose the Bussgang-aided Kalman filter (BKF). To this end, we first introduce the Bussgang theorem, which transforms \mathbf{r}_t into an equivalent linearized model. Building upon this, we develop the BKF algorithm. It is worth noting that BKF assumes that the state dynamics and observation models, i.e., $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$, $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$, and the distributions of \mathbf{w}_t and \mathbf{v}_t are fully known. We relax this assumption later.

A. Bussgang Decomposition

The Bussgang theorem, originally introduced in [29], states that the cross-correlation between a Gaussian input and an output of a memoryless nonlinear operation (e.g., quantization or clipping) is proportional to the input autocorrelation. Specifically, assume a zero-mean Gaussian signal \mathbf{y} with covariance matrix \mathbf{C}_y and a distorted signal $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y})$, which corresponds to (13). For clarity and notational convenience, the time index is omitted hereafter. Then, using the Bussgang theorem, the correlation between \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{y} satisfies the following relationship:

$$\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{C}_y, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{y}} \triangleq \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{r}\mathbf{y}^\top]$ represents the correlation matrix between zero-mean vectors \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{y} . Additionally, the Bussgang coefficient matrix \mathbf{B} is computed as

$$\mathbf{B} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \text{diag}(\mathbf{C}_y)^{-\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (16)$$

Leveraging (16), the output signal \mathbf{r} of the distortion function $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$ is decomposed in terms of the original signal \mathbf{y} as follows:

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y}) \approx \mathbf{B}\mathbf{y} + \boldsymbol{\eta}, \quad (17)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ is a zero-mean non-Gaussian noise vector that is uncorrelated with both \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{y} .

When an input to the distortion function $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$ has non-zero mean, the Bussgang decomposition becomes complicated. Specifically, consider

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}) = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{z}), \quad (18)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \neq 0$ denotes the mean of the input signal, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{z}] = \boldsymbol{\gamma}$. Considering the mean of the input signal, the Bussgang decomposition leads to

$$\mathbf{r} = \hat{\mathbf{r}} + \boldsymbol{\eta} = (\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{r}] + \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{y}} \cdot \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{y}}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{y}) + \boldsymbol{\eta}, \quad (19)$$

which can be interpreted as the LMMSE estimate $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ of \mathbf{r} plus a noise term $\boldsymbol{\eta}$. Here, the correlation matrix $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{y}}$ between \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{y} , as derived in (15), is expressed as $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{y}} = \bar{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{y}}$, where $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$ is a diagonal matrix whose (i, i) -th element is given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{B}}[i, i] = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{y}}[i, i]}} \exp\left(-\frac{\boldsymbol{\gamma}[i]^2}{2\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{y}}[i, i]}\right). \quad (20)$$

Additionally, the mean of the output signal \mathbf{r} is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{r}[n]] = \text{erf}\left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\gamma}[n]}{\sqrt{2\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{y}}[n, n]}}\right), \quad (21)$$

where $\text{erf}(\cdot)$ denotes the Gaussian error function. Under the additional assumption that \mathbf{y} is linearly related to another Gaussian random variable \mathbf{x} with covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{x}}$, as in our state estimation problem, the LMMSE estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ of \mathbf{x} based on the linearized \mathbf{r} is given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}] + \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}}^{-1} (\mathbf{r} - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{r}]), \quad (22)$$

where the cross-covariance between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{r} is $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{y}} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T$. This expression, derived by applying (19), can be easily computed using only standard matrix operations. In contrast, the (m, n) entry of the covariance matrix of \mathbf{r} is given by

$$\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{r}}[m, n] = \mathbb{E}\left[(\mathbf{y}[m] - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[m]]) (\mathbf{y}[n] - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[n]])\right] \quad (23)$$

$$= \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[m]\mathbf{y}[n]] - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[m]]\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[n]], \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[m]\mathbf{y}[n]]$ is given as in (25). Following this expression, applying the Bussgang decomposition with non-zero input requires computing the covariance of \mathbf{r}_t , involving double integrals over all matrix elements. Consequently, this leads to prohibitively high computational complexity. In addition to the computational burden, a non-zero mean input intensifies the information loss introduced by 1-bit ADCs.

To address this issue, we adopt a dithering technique that deliberately adds noise to the input signal. Equivalently, dithering can be viewed as dynamically shifting the quantization thresholds, as the added noise effectively modifies the decision boundaries. Namely, when a dithering vector $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is applied, the quantization function $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y}_t - \boldsymbol{\tau}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{y}[i] > \boldsymbol{\tau}[i], \\ -1, & \mathbf{y}[i] \leq \boldsymbol{\tau}[i]. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Careful design of the dithering vector $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is essential for making the Bussgang decomposition computationally tractable and for improving the ensuing state estimation accuracy. In the 1-bit quantization regime, centering the input signal—by subtracting its predicted mean—is advantageous because a symmetric (zero-mean) distribution fully exploits the quantizer's dynamic range: positive and negative deviations are equally likely to cross the zero decision threshold. From an information-theoretic viewpoint, zero-mean signaling is known

to maximize the mutual information between the quantizer input and output under a fixed power constraint. For instance, the prior studies on binary-output channels show that the capacity-achieving distribution is binary-antipodal, which is necessarily zero-mean [30], [31]. Conversely, a non-zero mean biases the input toward a single quantization region, thereby reducing the output entropy and increasing information loss.

Motivated by the above intuition, we design the dithering vector $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ for zero-centering the input signal. Given the measurement model $\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_t) + \mathbf{v}_t$, the zero-centered signal delivered to the quantizer is obtained by $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_t]$, so that

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y}_t - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_t]), \quad \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_t] = \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}, \quad (27)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}$ is the one-step prediction obtained from the previous estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-1}$.

Since we have $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1} | \mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{t-1}] = \mathbf{0}$ by construction, the input signal to the quantizer has zero mean. Based on this construction, we develop the BKF algorithm in the next subsection.

B. Bussgang-aided Kalman Filter

Based on the insights of the previous subsection, at time t , the input to the 1-bit ADC is formed as $\mathbf{z}_t = \mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}$ with proper dithering. This construction guarantees that the input to the quantizer is zero-mean, thereby minimizing the information loss and also simplifying the analytical computations on the Bussgang decomposition. Now, by applying the Bussgang decomposition to \mathbf{r}_t , we obtain:

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{z}_t) = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}) \quad (28)$$

$$= \mathbf{B}_t \mathbf{z}_t + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \text{diag}(\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1})^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{z}_t + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t. \quad (29)$$

Here, $\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1}$ is the error covariance matrix of the dithered input signal \mathbf{z}_t , and also represents the error covariance matrix of the measurement signal \mathbf{y}_t , defined in the same manner as (7). The Bussgang coefficient matrix \mathbf{B}_t is derived as per (16), i.e., $\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \text{diag}(\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1})^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. As a result, (29) provides a linear approximation of the nonlinearly quantized signal \mathbf{r}_t with \mathbf{z}_t , which is essential for constructing a tractable and recursive state tracking mechanism.

As explained earlier, the effective noise $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t$ is uncorrelated with both the residual input signal \mathbf{z}_t and the quantized output \mathbf{r}_t , and follows a non-Gaussian distribution. However, for analytical tractability, we approximate $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t$ as zero-mean Gaussian noise, following common practice in EKF and UKF, where non-Gaussian effects are approximated under Gaussian assumptions for tractable state estimation. Based on this approximation, the proposed BKF proceeds with the following prediction and update steps.

- 1) **Prediction step:** Let the current time step be t . Based on the posterior state moments up to time $t-1$, we compute the prior statistical moments as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-1}), \quad (30)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{F}_t \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t-1|t-1} \mathbf{F}_t^T + \mathbf{Q}_t, \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbb{E}[y[m]y[n]] = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{-\gamma[m]} \int_{-\infty}^{-\gamma[n]} p(y[m], y[n]) dy[m]dy[n] + 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\gamma[m]} \int_{-\infty}^{\gamma[n]} p(y[m], y[n]) dy[m]dy[n] - 1 \quad (25)$$

(a) Overall filtering architecture

(b) Busssgang gain calculation for BKF

(c) Busssgang gain calculation for BKNet

Fig. 2. (a) Overall architecture with (b) BKF and (c) BKNet.

Similarly, the prior mean and error covariance of \mathbf{y}_t are obtained from the prior state statistical moments $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$ and $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$.

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}), \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{H}_t \Sigma_{t|t-1} \mathbf{H}_t^\top + \mathbf{R}_t, \quad (33)$$

We note that the prior moments of the residual input to the quantizer \mathbf{z}_t are obtained as

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_{t|t-1} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1}] = 0, \quad (34)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_{t|t-1} = \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1})(\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t|t-1})^\top] = \mathbf{P}_{t|t-1}. \quad (35)$$

From the Busssgang decomposition (29) and by defining $\mathbf{D}_{t|t-1} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1})^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ for computational convenience, the prior observation statistical moments are given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{t|t-1} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{z}_t)] = 0, \quad (36)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{t|t-1} = \frac{2}{\pi} \arcsin[\mathbf{D}_{t|t-1} \cdot \mathbf{P}_{t|t-1} \cdot \mathbf{D}_{t|t-1}], \quad (37)$$

where (33) is derived by applying Price's theorem [32] to (23). This derivation assumes that the input mean satisfies $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}[n]] = 0$. After completing the prediction step, we proceed to the update step.

- 2) **Update step:** In this step, we compute the posterior state statistical moments at time t using the results of the prediction step. Exploiting the linearized model and Gaussian approximation, we readily obtain the posterior moments as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{r}_t, \quad (38)$$

$$\Sigma_t = \Sigma_{t|t-1} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1} \cdot \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t^\top. \quad (39)$$

Crucially, $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t$ is the Busssgang gain, derived as

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t = \Sigma_{t|t-1} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_t \cdot \mathbf{H}_t)^\top \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^{-1}. \quad (40)$$

Similar to the Kalman gain, which corrects the predicted state using observations (10), the Busssgang gain serves to adjust the prediction based on 1-bit measurements.

In particular, the nonlinear effect of quantization is approximated through a linear transformation that preserves the second-order statistics of the residual input signal, enabling a structured interpretation of the quantized data.

The architecture of BKF is summarized schematically in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b).

Remark 2 (Linearization principle in BKF and EKF). In both the EKF and the proposed BKF, a key strategy to achieve a tractable state estimation mechanism is the linearization of an otherwise intractable nonlinearity. In EKF, the SS models are linearized using a first-order Jacobian expansion, thereby approximating nonlinear system dynamics with an equivalent linear model and associated Gaussian state uncertainty. This linearization allows the Kalman filter to operate efficiently, providing recursive prediction and update steps despite the underlying nonlinearity of the system dynamics. By doing this, EKF retains the tractability of the Kalman filtering framework. In BKF, the inherently nonlinear 1-bit quantizer is linearized through the Bussgang decomposition, which yields an equivalent linear observation model with noise, thereby facilitating the application of Kalman filtering techniques. While the objects of linearization are different, i.e., the system dynamics in EKF and the measurement quantization in BKF, the underlying approach is similar: both approaches replace the dominant nonlinearity with a statistically consistent linear surrogate, ensuring that the power and efficiency of Kalman filtering are retained.

C. Reduced Bussgang-aided Kalman Filter

Despite the efficient linearization via the Bussgang decomposition, the information loss introduced by 1-bit quantization remains inevitable. To compensate for this, it is natural to use a large number of 1-bit ADCs ($n > m$) to capture sufficient information for accurate state estimation. Generally, since hardware energy consumption increases exponentially with the number of quantization bits [33], [34], deploying many 1-bit ADCs results in significantly lower energy consumption compared to using a small number of high-resolution (ideal) ADCs. Nonetheless, this requires processing the high-dimensional vector \mathbf{r}_t as indicated in (38) and (39). Specifically, a critical computational step in deriving the Bussgang gain \mathbf{BG}_t involves inverting the matrix $\mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}$, which incurs a computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$.

To address this issue, we develop the reduced-BKF (rBKF), which modifies the original BKF framework by reducing the dimension of the observation vector. To this end, in rBKF, we first obtain a lower-dimensional 1-bit observation vector by projecting \mathbf{r}_t onto a given matrix \mathbf{A} , i.e.,

$$\mathbf{r}_t^* = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{r}_t, \quad (41)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{an \times n}$ and $1/a$ is the number of ADCs used per measurement feature. Here we have $0 < a < 1$ and $an \in \mathbb{N}$. Based on (41), the resulting reduced observation vector $\mathbf{r}_t^* \in \mathbb{R}^{an}$ is used for state estimation. The performance of rBKF may depend on the design of the projection operator \mathbf{A} . This paper adopts a simple design for \mathbf{A} in which each entry represents the average of the corresponding measurement

feature, with more advanced design strategies deferred to future work. Specifically, the projection operator \mathbf{A} is defined as

$$\mathbf{A} = a \cdot \mathbf{1}_{1/a}^\top \otimes \mathbf{I}_{an}. \quad (42)$$

Accordingly, the measurement function $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$ is reformulated by $\mathbf{h}(\cdot) = \mathbf{1}_{1/a} \otimes \tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\cdot)$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\cdot)$ denotes the measurement function corresponding to the case in which exactly one ADC is used per measurement feature.

Since the input-output relationship has changed according to (41), the Bussgang gain for rBKF needs to be recomputed. By incorporating the reduced-dimensional matrix \mathbf{A} , the covariance matrices are modified as follows:

$$\mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^* = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{r}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{r}_t^{*\top}] = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1} \cdot \mathbf{A}^\top, \quad (43)$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_t \cdot \mathbf{r}_{t|t-1}^*] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_t \cdot \mathbf{r}_t^\top] \cdot \mathbf{A}^\top. \quad (44)$$

From this, the modified Bussgang gain for rBKF is derived as follows:

$$\mathbf{BG}_t^* = \Sigma_{t|t-1} \cdot (\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}_t \cdot \mathbf{H}_t)^\top \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^{*-1} \quad (45)$$

$$= \Sigma_{t|t-1} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{H}_t)^\top \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^{*-1}. \quad (46)$$

Consequently, in rBKF, the update step of BKF (38), (39) is modified to:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} + \mathbf{BG}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{r}_t^*, \quad (47)$$

$$\Sigma_{t|t} = \Sigma_{t|t-1} - \mathbf{BG}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^* \cdot \mathbf{BG}_t^{*\top}. \quad (48)$$

It is worth noting that rBKF requires only $\mathcal{O}((a^3 + a)n^3)$ computational complexity, as the most expensive operation (matrix inversion of the observation error covariance) is performed on a reduced matrix of dimension $a \cdot n$. Later, we show through numerical experiments that, despite this dimensionality reduction, rBKF achieves estimation performance comparable to the case where the full observation vector is used.

IV. BUSSGANG-AIDED KALMANNET

Although the proposed BKF and rBKF effectively address the state estimation problem under 1-bit quantization, they require perfect knowledge of the state dynamics and observation models, including $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$, $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$, and the distributions of \mathbf{w}_t and \mathbf{v}_t . However, as discussed in [8], obtaining such model knowledge in practice is often not straightforward. In this section, we develop the Bussgang-aided KalmanNet (BKNet), a learning-based counterpart to BKF that does not rely on explicit knowledge of the system dynamics or noise models.

BKF reveals that by leveraging the Bussgang decomposition and dithering, state estimation under 1-bit quantization can be effectively performed through a structured linear recursion. Building on this insight, we design BKNet to preserve the core structure of the BKF by learning only the Bussgang gain \mathbf{BG}_t , rather than approximating the entire filtering process in an end-to-end manner. This approach not only reduces the learning complexity but also retains the model-aware inductive bias inherent in the original BKF formulation. We describe the detailed process of BKNet as follows.

A. High Level Architecture

We use rBKF as the foundation for designing BKNet. This is because when $a < 1$ (the typical scenario), rBKF not only decreases the computational complexity associated with the computation of the Busssgang gain matrix \mathbf{BG}_t (46), but also effectively reduces the number of parameters required in a DNN by decreasing the matrix dimension. Moreover, rBKF retains generality in that it reduces to the original BKF when the reduction ratio is set to $a = 1$ and the projection operator is chosen as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}$. This implies that rBKF encompasses BKF as a special case, while offering additional flexibility for complexity–performance trade-offs.

Based on the rBKF formulation with \mathbf{r}_t^* in (47), the BKNet architecture is constructed as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1} + \mathcal{BG}_t(\Theta) \cdot \mathbf{r}_t^*. \quad (49)$$

Regarding (49), we make some discussions as follows.

Remark 3 (BKNet architecture). In (49), $\mathcal{BG}_t(\Theta)$ denotes the Busssgang gain learned via a DNN, where Θ represents the set of trainable parameters. This formulation preserves the recursive update structure of rBKF while replacing the analytically derived Busssgang gain \mathbf{BG}_t^* with a data-driven surrogate mapping function $\mathcal{BG}_t(\Theta)$. Similar to rBKF, $\mathcal{BG}_t(\Theta)$ performs the correction to the predicted state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1}$ by exploiting the quantized measurements \mathbf{r}_t^* , where the balance between the prior prediction and the new observation is learned in a data-driven manner. This allows BKNet to compensate for modeling imperfections and to generalize across varying system conditions. We also note that the design of BKNet follows the paradigm of model-based deep learning [27], wherein DNNs are embedded into well-established algorithmic structures to enhance flexibility while retaining domain knowledge. In this sense, BKNet shares structural similarities with KalmanNet [8], in that both adopt a recursive prediction–correction architecture and focus on learning the correction gain instead of modeling the entire state estimation process end-to-end. However, a key distinction lies in the observation model. Whereas KalmanNet assumes continuous-valued ideal measurements, BKNet is specifically designed to operate under extremely coarse (1-bit) quantized observations, which introduces additional nonlinearity and information loss that must be compensated through learning.

B. Learning Structure

Motivated by the analytical form of the Busssgang gain \mathbf{BG}_t (46), the learning block of BKNet is designed to effectively capture its dependence on the second-order statistics. Specifically, dropping the time index subscript t for notational convenience, the Busssgang gain \mathbf{BG} is composed of: 1) the prior state error covariance Σ , 2) the inverse observation error covariance \mathbf{S} , and 3) the Busssgang coefficient matrix \mathbf{B} . Furthermore, Σ is obtained based on the process noise covariance \mathbf{Q} and the previously obtained posterior state error covariance $\tilde{\Sigma}$. Also, \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{B} are derived from the measurement error covariance \mathbf{P} , which is governed by \mathbf{R} .

Leveraging this analytical dependency, BKNet employs three GRUs, each representing one of the fundamental matrices \mathbf{Q} , Σ , and \mathbf{P} , which form the basis of the Busssgang gain computation. The overall architecture and the GRU-based learning structure for the Busssgang gain are illustrated in Figs. 2(a) and 2(c). Also, we summarize the input, hidden state, and output structures of each GRU module in Table I. For notational convenience, we denote the fully-connected input embedding layer (hereafter, the projection layer) as the function $\text{FC}(\cdot; \Theta)$, where Θ represents trainable parameters. Additionally, we use $[\mathbf{a}; \mathbf{b}]$ to denote the concatenation of vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , and $\text{vec}(\cdot)$ to denote the flattening of matrices. In the following, we provide a detailed description and the underlying intuition for each GRU component, as well as the overall architecture.

- 1) **GRU Q**: To calculate the Busssgang gain, the prior state error covariance must first be obtained, which depends on the state noise covariance matrix \mathbf{Q}_t . Here, \mathbf{Q}_t can be inferred from the difference between previous state estimates, given by $\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-1} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-2|t-2}$. To this end, the input feature vector $\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is expanded via the projection layer into an embedding vector of dimension m^2 (i.e., $\mathbf{Q}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$), which is then fed into the GRU \mathbf{Q} . The hidden state uses \mathbf{Q}_{t-1} , the previous output of GRU \mathbf{Q} . The features of GRU \mathbf{Q} are summarized as follows.
- 2) **GRU Σ** : Next, $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ is modeled using the covariance of $(\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t-1})$. Thus, $\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-1} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1|t-2}$ is used as an input feature for the corresponding GRU. Moreover, as shown in (31), $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ can also be expressed in terms of the previous posterior error covariance $\Sigma_{t-1|t-1}$ and \mathbf{Q}_t . Therefore, \mathbf{Q}_t obtained from the GRU \mathbf{Q} is also used as an input feature, while the hidden state employs $\Sigma_{t-1|t-1}$ that was previously updated via a FC-layer. Details regarding the term $\Sigma_{t-1|t-1}$ will be explained later. The features of GRU Σ are summarized as follows.
- 3) **GRU P**: Among the components that constitute the Busssgang gain, $\mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}$ and \mathbf{B}_t are derived from the measurement error covariance $\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1}$, which is computed as a function of $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ and \mathbf{R}_t . In our design, $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ is provided by the GRU Σ , and to match the dimensions of the measurement error covariance $\mathbf{P}_{t|t-1}$, it is projected from m^2 to n^2 via a projection layer before being used as an input feature. The component $\mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}$ is obtained from the residual $\Delta\mathbf{r}_t = \mathbf{r}_t^* - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{t-1}^*$. However, since \mathbf{R}_t cannot be directly inferred from the quantized observations, we use the difference $\Delta\hat{\mathbf{r}}_t = \mathbf{r}_t^* - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{t|t-1}^* = \mathbf{r}_t^*$ as a surrogate input feature to capture the effect of the measurement noise covariance. Consequently, GRU \mathbf{P} generates $\mathbf{B}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^{*-1}$ as its output and employs its previous output, $\mathbf{B}_{t-1}^* \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t-1|t-1}^{*-1}$, as the hidden state to preserve memory. The features of GRU \mathbf{P} are summarized as follows.
- 4) **FC-layer**: To further enhance the computational flow of BKNet, we employ three additional FC-layers. The first layer is used to combine $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ and $\mathbf{B}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^{*-1}$, obtained from GRU Σ and GRU \mathbf{P} . In particular, since this layer is responsible for producing the final Busssgang gain, we add a hidden layer to enhance its generalization performance.

TABLE I
INPUT, HIDDEN STATE, AND OUTPUT DEFINITIONS OF THE GRU MODULES IN BKNET

	GRU \mathbf{Q}	GRU Σ	GRU \mathbf{P}
Input	$\text{FC}(\Delta\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1}; \Theta)$	$[\text{FC}([\text{vec}(\mathbf{Q}_t); \Delta\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t-1}]; \Theta); \text{vec}(\mathbf{Q}_t)]$	$[\text{FC}(\text{vec}(\Sigma_{t t-1}); \Theta); \text{FC}([\Delta\mathbf{r}_t; \Delta\hat{\mathbf{r}}_t]; \Theta)]$
Hidden state	$\text{vec}(\mathbf{Q}_{t-1})$	$\text{vec}(\Sigma_{t-1 t-1})$	$\text{vec}(\mathbf{B}_{t-1}^{*\top} \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t-1 t-2}^{*-1})$
Output	$\text{vec}(\mathbf{Q}_t)$	$\text{vec}(\Sigma_{t t-1})$	$\text{vec}(\mathbf{B}_t^{*\top} \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t t-1}^{*-1})$

The remaining two layers serve to update $\Sigma_{t|t}$, which is used as the hidden state of GRU Σ . According to (48), to compute $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t^* \cdot \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^* \cdot \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}_t^{*\top}$, the outputs from the FC-layer that generates the Bussgang gain and the GRU \mathbf{P} are passed through an FC-layer. Subsequently, the resulting output and $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ are passed through an additional FC-layer to finally obtain the posterior state error covariance at the current time step.

This specific architectural design, incorporating the 3-GRU sequential structure and the Σ update feedback, is an intentional mapping of each GRU to the analytical components of rBKF (\mathbf{Q} , Σ , and \mathbf{P}). We hypothesize that this model-based deep learning approach not only enhances the model's interpretability by aligning the filtering steps with neural network components but also maximizes estimation performance by effectively capturing the underlying statistical dependencies. The justification for adopting this 3-GRU and backward-pass structure over simpler alternatives will be quantitatively validated through a detailed ablation study in Section V-E.

C. Training Algorithm

BKNet adopts an end-to-end supervised learning approach in which the observed sequence $\mathbf{r}_{1:T}$ is fed into the DNN sequentially, and the entire resulting sequence of estimates is compared against the corresponding ground truth values. We use the MSE as the loss function, defined by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \ell_t = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \|\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t}\|^2, \quad (50)$$

for a single data sequence. To verify the feasibility of back-propagation through the DNN, we compute the gradient of the instantaneous loss ℓ_t with respect to the Bussgang gain as:

$$\frac{\partial \ell_t}{\partial \mathcal{B}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)} = \frac{\partial \|\mathcal{B}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)\mathbf{r}_t^* - \Delta\mathbf{x}_t\|^2}{\partial \mathcal{B}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)} \quad (51)$$

$$= 2(\mathcal{B}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)\mathbf{r}_t^* - \Delta\mathbf{x}_t) \cdot \mathbf{r}_t^{*\top}, \quad (52)$$

where $\Delta\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t}$. Since the model is differentiable with respect to $\mathcal{B}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)$, the training process can be performed directly without requiring any auxiliary optimization steps. In other words, to maintain stable gradient propagation, \mathbf{r}_t^* is treated as a stop-gradient variable. In practice, gradient flow through the quantization operation is prevented by detaching the estimated state from the computational graph during back-propagation.

The training dataset consists of N sequence pairs $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{R}_i, \mathbf{X}_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where each is defined as:

$$\mathbf{X}_i = [\mathbf{x}_1^{(i)}, \mathbf{x}_2^{(i)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_T^{(i)}], \quad \mathbf{R}_i = [\mathbf{r}_1^{(i)}, \mathbf{r}_2^{(i)}, \dots, \mathbf{r}_T^{(i)}]. \quad (53)$$

To mitigate model overfitting, we include a regularization term to obtain the following loss function for a single sequence data i :

$$\mathcal{L}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{T_i} \sum_{t=1}^{T_i} \|\mathbf{x}_t^{(i)} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t}(\mathbf{r}_t^{(i)}; \Theta)\|^2 + \lambda \|\Theta\|^2, \quad (54)$$

where λ is the coefficient for balancing data fit and model complexity. BKNet trains the model parameters Θ by minimizing the mini-batch loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_k^{\text{mini-batch}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_k|} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}_k} \mathcal{L}^{(j)}, \quad (55)$$

where \mathcal{B}_k indicates the k -th mini-batch set and $|\mathcal{B}_k| = B$ denotes the mini-batch size. We adopt the Adam optimizer [35], updating Θ at each iteration based on adaptive estimates of the first and second moments of the gradients.

Remark 4 (Discussion). State estimation under imperfect model knowledge is a fundamentally challenging problem due to model mismatch. To overcome this, various solutions, ranging from an end-to-end data-driven approach [7] to a model-based DNN approach [8], [9], have been proposed. This work considers a more challenging setting, in which model knowledge is imperfect and also measurements are quantized to 1 bit per observation, a combination that renders conventional state estimation methods ineffective. BKNet is designed to integrate several complementary techniques for effectively handling both model mismatch and extreme quantization. First, to alleviate the severe information loss inherent in 1-bit observations, a dithering technique is exploited to shift inputs toward quantization thresholds, as done in BKF. To this end, the prior measurement prediction, derived from the previous state estimate, is fed into the ADC to update its threshold at the current time step. Additionally, BKNet effectively leverages the GRU architecture to capture temporal dependencies inherent in sequential data, enabling robust estimation even under partially known system models. The dithered observations serve as salient features for the GRU by emphasizing subtle changes and patterns in the data, thereby further enhancing the GRU's ability to capture hidden system dynamics. As a result, BKNet compensates for prediction error caused by model mismatch, demonstrating robustness against uncertainties between the actual system and its approximate model.

D. Stability Analysis

It is worthwhile to analyze the stability of the algorithms proposed in Sections III and IV. The stability of the model-based filters, BKF and rBKF, is demonstrated through the

convergence properties of their underlying algorithms. First, by substituting the Bussgang gain definition from (40) into the posterior covariance update equation (39), we rewrite $\Sigma_{t|t}$ as follows:

$$\Sigma_{t|t} = \Sigma_{t|t-1} - \Sigma_{t|t-1}(\mathbf{H}_t^{\text{eff}})^\top \mathbf{S}_{t|t-1}^{-1}(\mathbf{H}_t^{\text{eff}})\Sigma_{t|t-1}, \quad (56)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_t^{\text{eff}} \triangleq \mathbf{B}_t \mathbf{H}_t$ is the effective observation matrix incorporating the Bussgang coefficient matrix. Then, the error covariance recursion for BKF, defined for the prior covariance $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$, can be expressed as (57). This formulation corresponds to a standard form of the Discrete-time Riccati Equation (DRE) [36]. Therefore, under the standard assumptions where \mathbf{F}_t and $\mathbf{Q}_t^{1/2}$ are uniformly stabilizable and \mathbf{F}_t and $\mathbf{H}_t^{\text{eff}}$ are uniformly detectable, the solution $\Sigma_{t|t-1}$ to this DRE is guaranteed to converge to a unique positive semi-definite solution and remain uniformly bounded. Since the posterior covariance always satisfies $\Sigma_{t|t} \leq \Sigma_{t|t-1}$, $\Sigma_{t|t}$ is also uniformly bounded. This result theoretically establishes the stability of the BKF, demonstrating that convergence is guaranteed even when the severe 1-bit nonlinearity is linearized via the Bussgang statistical approximation. The stability analysis extends directly to rBKF. As introduced in Section III-C, rBKF applies a constant linear projection matrix \mathbf{A} to the observation model. This modifies the effective observation matrix to $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{H}_t^{\text{eff}}$, and the resulting covariance update still forms a standard DRE, with the detectability assumption now placed on the pair $(\mathbf{F}_t, \mathbf{A}\mathbf{H}_t^{\text{eff}})$. Since this condition holds under the same general assumptions, the error covariance $\Sigma_{t|t}$ for rBKF is also guaranteed to be uniformly bounded.

The stability of the data-driven model, BKNet, is ensured by a related but distinct line of reasoning. Since the rBKF framework is provably convergent, the stability of BKNet can be characterized by that of its learned gain. If the GRU-based network produces a bounded (i.e., stable) gain $\mathcal{B}\mathcal{G}_t(\Theta)$ at each time step, the overall filter inherits the proven convergence of the rBKF. Therefore, because the training loss function (50) is equivalent to minimizing $\text{Tr}(\Sigma_{t|t})$, the optimization process of minimizing the MSE encourages the network to learn parameters Θ that produce a bounded gain. Under this assumption on the learned gain, the overall stability of BKNet follows from the proven convergence of the rBKF framework.

V. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we first evaluate the proposed BKF and rBKF to validate the soundness of our DNN architecture, and then assess the performance of BKNet. As baseline methods, we consider 1) EKF when the model knowledge is known and 2) KalmanNet [8] when the model knowledge is not known. We note that in [8], KalmanNet and EKF were shown to outperform most of the conventional state estimation algorithms such as particle filter, UKF and the end-to-end DNN-based methods. We focus on two nonlinear SS models to evaluate the performance: 1) the Lorenz attractor, a well-known chaotic system used to benchmark nonlinear state estimation methods, and 2) the Michigan NCLT dataset [28], which provides real-world sensor measurements for large-scale mobile robot navigation.

A. Network Architecture Setups

Before proceeding to the results for specific scenarios, we outline the common implementation details used for all deep learning models to ensure reproducibility.

Regarding the network architecture, the hidden state dimension of each GRU was determined by the size of the specific covariance or gain matrix it was designed to track. To provide the GRUs with a sufficiently expressive representation, the input features were first passed through a fully connected layer that expanded their dimensionality by a factor of five. The final Bussgang Gain was then generated by a separate FC output layer containing 40 hidden nodes. Both expansion factor and the output layer size were chosen to offer a practical balance between representational capacity and model complexity, as previously demonstrated in [8]. These settings allow multiple residual and state difference based features to be embedded effectively within a shared latent space, and were therefore adopted in our model. Network initialization was also standardized. The prior for the process noise covariance \mathbf{Q} was set to the identity matrix \mathbf{I}_m . All other priors were initialized with random matrices sampled from a standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. The initial hidden state for each GRU was then set by flattening its corresponding prior matrix, providing a meaningful starting point for the filtering process.

All models were trained using the Adam optimizer with a fixed learning rate of 5×10^{-4} . To prevent overfitting, L2 regularization (weight decay) with a coefficient of 1×10^{-3} was applied. Furthermore, gradient clipping with a maximum norm of 1.0 was used to ensure training stability. The optimal model was selected based on validation performance, which was evaluated at every training step.

B. Lorenz Attractor Setups

To ensure a fair and rigorous comparison with prior work, we adopt the same experimental setup as in the KalmanNet study [8], where the Lorenz attractor served as a primary benchmark. The Lorenz system is particularly suitable for evaluating our method because it exhibits highly nonlinear and chaotic dynamics, making state estimation extremely challenging. The continuous-time dynamics of the Lorenz system are described by the Jacobian matrix:

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_\tau) = \begin{pmatrix} -\sigma & \sigma & 0 \\ \rho - x_{3,\tau} & -1 & -x_{1,\tau} \\ x_{2,\tau} & x_{1,\tau} & -\beta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (58)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_\tau = [x_{1,\tau}, x_{2,\tau}, x_{3,\tau}]^\top$ denotes the state vector at time τ . We follow the classical Lorenz parameters $\sigma = 10$, $\rho = 28$, and $\beta = 8/3$. In particular, the inclusion of the state variable $x_{1,\tau}$, $x_{2,\tau}$, and $x_{3,\tau}$ in each entry introduces the system's complex nonlinearity. To discretize the continuous-time model with sampling interval $\Delta\tau$, we approximate the matrix exponential $\exp(\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_\tau)\Delta\tau)$ by truncating its Taylor series expansion at order J . Accordingly, we define the fundamental solution matrix as:

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_\tau) \triangleq \mathbf{I} + \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{(\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_\tau) \cdot \Delta\tau)^j}{j!}, \quad (59)$$

$$\Sigma_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{F}_t(\Sigma_{t-1|t-2} - \Sigma_{t-1|t-2}(\mathbf{H}_{t-1}^{\text{eff}})^{\top} \mathbf{S}_{t-1|t-2}^{-1}(\mathbf{H}_{t-1}^{\text{eff}})\Sigma_{t-1|t-2})\mathbf{F}_t^{\top} + \mathbf{Q}_t, \quad (57)$$

TABLE II
NUMERICAL MSE [DB] FOR LORENZ ATTRACTOR

Ideal observation		1-bit observation			
EKF	KalmanNet	EKF	KalmanNet	BKF	BKNet
-19.31	-19.49	17.85	12.95	-17.38	-17.31

In our experiments, we set $J = 5$. Finally, the discrete-time state model is expressed as

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_t) = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_t) \cdot \mathbf{x}_t, \quad (60)$$

and is used at each time t to predict the state at time $t + 1$.

For convenience, we assume that the measurement matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\cdot)$, corresponding to a single ADC per measurement feature, is given by $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\cdot) = \mathbf{I}_{qn}$. The training dataset comprises N paired sequences $\{(\mathbf{Y}_i, \mathbf{X}_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where \mathbf{Y}_i and \mathbf{X}_i denote the i -th measurement sequence and state sequence, respectively. The quantized observation sequence \mathbf{R}_i is obtained by applying proper dithering based on the previous estimate, as shown in Fig. 2. We use sequence length of 100 for training and 2000 for testing. In all the cases, we adopt the MSE expressed in decibels as the evaluation metric:

$$\text{MSE [dB]} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{NT_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^{T_i} \|\mathbf{x}_t - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t|t}\|^2 \right). \quad (61)$$

C. Evaluation of BKF and BKNet

In the first experiment—assuming full knowledge of the system model—we apply BKF and BKNet to 1-bit quantized observations, while EKF and KalmanNet use ideal (unquantized) observations. We compare their state estimation performance using a single ADC per measurement, under the settings $\frac{1}{r^2} = 10$ dB and SNR to -20 dB.

As shown in Fig. 3 and Table II, applying EKF and KalmanNet directly to the 1-bit observations produces no meaningful estimates, whereas our BKF and BKNet achieve satisfactory estimation performance. Furthermore, although BKF and BKNet with 1-bit observations perform slightly worse than EKF and KalmanNet under ideal (unquantized) observations, the performance gap remains small, indicating that accurate state estimation is attainable using only a single ADC per observation element. This finding is significant because it demonstrates that accurate state estimation is achievable even under severe quantization distortion by using the Bussgang decomposition and dithering, thereby supporting the feasibility of state estimation based on 1-bit observations.

D. Reduced-BKF

Next, we explore the performance and inference time of rBKF and BKF when multiple ADCs are used per measurement feature. We set the number of 1-bit ADCs per measurement feature to 1, 8, 64, and 128, respectively. We consider two scenarios: one in which all ADCs share identical measurement noise, and another in which the measurement noise is heterogeneous across ADCs.

TABLE III
BKF & rBKF, # OF ADC VS INFERENCE TIME [S], IDENTICAL NOISE

$1/a$	1	8	64	128
EKF (ideal observation)	0.601			
BKF	0.691	0.777	2.746	5.428
rBKF	0.720	0.732	0.740	0.894

TABLE IV
BKF & rBKF, # OF ADC VS MSE [DB], HETEROGENEOUS NOISE

$1/a$	1	8	64	128
EKF (ideal observation)	-22.41			
BKF	-20.53	-26.59	-31.80	-33.79
rBKF	-20.53	-26.33	-31.45	-33.33

1) *Identical noise*: In the scenario where all ADCs have identical measurement noise, i.e., $\mathbf{R} = r^2\mathbf{I}$, we fix the SNR at -20 dB. We evaluate the estimation performance of BKF and rBKF by varying $\frac{1}{r^2}$ from -10 dB to 30 dB. We plot the results in Fig. 4. For any fixed number of ADCs, BKF and rBKF exhibit identical performance across all measurement noise levels, confirming that under identical noise conditions, rBKF's averaging-based dimensionality reduction incurs no information loss. Remarkably, for $1/r^2$ values up to 20 dB, except when a single ADC is used per measurement feature, BKF and rBKF with 1-bit observations outperform the EKF using ideal observations. The inference times are reported in Table III. We compute the mean inference time for each ADC count by averaging processing times over all noise levels. In the single-ADC case, the computation of the projection operator \mathbf{A} introduces additional processing overhead to rBKF, resulting in an additional latency of 0.03 seconds. As the number of ADCs increases, rBKF achieves shorter inference times due to the dimensionality reduction in (41). Consequently, the inference time savings of rBKF over BKF become increasingly significant as the ADC count grows.

2) *Heterogeneous noise*: To reflect realistic system characteristics, we also conduct experiments under heterogeneous measurement noise conditions. In this case, we set the state noise variance such that $q^2 = -30$ dB, and for each ADC, we independently sample the measurement noise variance from a uniform distribution between -20 dB and -10 dB. The experimental results are presented in Table IV. This shows that the performance of BKF and rBKF improves as the number of ADCs increases. As in the identical-noise case, BKF and rBKF with 1-bit observations outperform the EKF using ideal observations for ADC counts greater than eight. However, under heterogeneous-noise conditions, reducing the dimensionality of the observation vector inevitably incurs some information loss. Consequently, rBKF's performance is slightly worse than BKF's, though the gap remains small.

These results reveal that employing multiple 1-bit ADCs effectively mitigates quantization distortion, even outperforming methods based on ideal observations with two ADCs per measurement. Moreover, the dimensionality reduction applied

Fig. 3. State estimation results for the Lorenz attractor using 1-bit observations.

Fig. 4. The MSE performance comparison of BKF and rBKF with identical noise.

in rBKF significantly decreases computational complexity, exhibiting negligible performance degradation.

E. BKNet

Now, we consider scenarios in which the system’s process and measurement noise statistics are unknown or only partially known. Before evaluating its robustness under various noise conditions and model mismatch scenarios (detailed in the following subsections), we first conduct an ablation study to validate the architectural design choices. As described in Section IV-B and illustrated in Fig. 2(c), BKNet employs a specific structure composed of three GRUs (for \mathbf{Q} , $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, and \mathbf{P}) connected sequentially, and includes a feedback path to update the hidden state of GRU $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ with the posterior state error covariance $\mathbf{\Sigma}_{t|t}$ (referred to as the ‘backward pass’). To justify this design, we evaluate the performance and complexity of several simplified variants of BKNet. The experiment is conducted under the same Lorenz attractor setup as in Section V-C. The performance and complexity of each variant are summarized in Table V. The results clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of our design choices by providing a comprehensive trade-off analysis between model complexity and estimation accuracy.

- **GRU×1 vs. Deeper Models:** The GRU×1 model has a significantly lower parameter count (2,697) and the fastest inference time (0.681s). However, its estimation performance (-14.32 dB) is substantially worse than all other configurations, indicating that this level of simplicity is insufficient to capture the complex dynamics required for accurate state estimation.

- **Justification of the Backward Pass:** We observe a clear benefit to including the backward pass for the $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ update. Comparing GRU×2 (Forward only) to GRU×2 (w/ Backward), the addition of the backward pass results in only a marginal increase in complexity (approx. 340 parameters) and inference time (approx. 0.075s). In contrast, this small cost yields a significant performance gain of 0.78 dB (from -16.26 dB to -17.04 dB). The similar trend is observed between GRU×3 (Forward only) and the proposed BKNet (a 0.79 dB gain for a similarly minor cost). This confirms that the posterior covariance feedback, which mimics the rBKF structure, is a highly efficient and necessary component.
- **Justification of the 3-GRU Structure:** When comparing the best 2-GRU model (GRU×2 (w/ Backward)) with the proposed BKNet (3-GRU w/ Backward), the cost of adding the third GRU (dedicated to \mathbf{Q}) is again very small: an increase of only 450 parameters (23,478 vs. 23,928) and less than 0.1s in inference time (0.973s vs. 1.062s). However, this addition provides a clear performance improvement from -17.04 dB to -17.31 dB. This demonstrates that sequentially modeling the distinct covariance components (\mathbf{Q} , $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, and \mathbf{P}) offers the best performance-to-complexity ratio among the tested variants.

Therefore, the proposed BKNet, which incorporates both the 3-GRU sequential architecture and the $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ update feedback, achieves the best estimation accuracy without incurring significant computational overhead compared to slightly simpler variants, validating it as our final model structure.

Next, we analyze its robustness to changes in ADC count and noise levels under both identical and heterogeneous noise conditions, and also verify whether the DNN can compensate for model mismatch. All experimental settings match those of the rBKF experiments in V-D.

1) *Identical noise:* Fig. 5 shows BKNet’s estimation performance as a function of the number of ADCs. Regardless of the ADC count, the estimation error decreases logarithmically with decreasing measurement noise magnitude. Notably, except when a single ADC is used per measurement feature, BKNet with 1-bit observations outperforms KalmanNet using ideal observations. Table VI shows the filtering times for different numbers of ADCs. Although the filtering time for BKNet increases slightly as the number of ADCs grows, this increase is negligible.

TABLE V
ABLATION STUDY ON BKNET ARCHITECTURE (COMPLEXITY VS. PERFORMANCE)

Model configuration	Description	Parameters	Inference time [s]	MSE [dB]
GRU×1	Single GRU (lumps \mathbf{Q} , Σ , \mathbf{P} estimation)	2,697	0.681	-14.32
GRU×2 (Forward only)	Two GRUs (e.g., for Σ and \mathbf{P} ; no backward pass)	23,136	0.898	-16.26
GRU×2 (w/ Backward)	Two GRUs (includes backward pass for Σ update)	23,478	0.973	-17.04
GRU×3 (Forward only)	Three GRUs (for \mathbf{Q} , Σ , \mathbf{P} ; no backward pass)	23,586	0.997	-16.52
BKNet (Proposed)	Three GRUs (includes backward pass)	23,928	1.062	-17.31

Fig. 5. BKNet, identical noise

TABLE VI
BKNET, # OF ADC VS INFERENCE TIME [S], IDENTICAL NOISE

$1/a$	1	8	64	128
KalmanNet (ideal observation)	1.014			
BKNet	1.032	1.032	1.037	1.049

2) *Heterogeneous noise*: Table VII shows that under heterogeneous noise, BKNet’s performance improves as the ADC count increases, outperforming the ideal-observation-based KalmanNet when more than one ADC is used per feature. This confirms that averaging-based dimensionality reduction is effective for both computational complexity and estimation performance, even in such conditions.

3) *Model mismatch*: In practical scenarios, it is difficult to obtain accurate information not only about the noise but also about the model functions. Therefore, we evaluate the estimation of BKNet’s performance under various model mismatch scenarios. We set $\frac{1}{r^2} = 10$ dB, the SNR is -20 dB, and assumed the simplest scenario with a single ADC per measurement feature.

- The first model-mismatch scenario is a state-evolution mismatch, referring to errors in the Taylor series expansion coefficients. While $J = 5$ is used during data generation, in this experiment the BKNet estimation is performed with $J = 1$. As shown in Table VIII, BKF exhibits an MSE of 6.24 dB—indicating poor estimation—whereas BKNet achieves -15.19 dB, which is close to the -17.39 dB obtained with full system knowledge.
- We next conduct an experiment under a model mismatch scenario in which the state evolution function is rotated by $\theta = 1^\circ$. The results indicate that, whereas BKF yields an MSE of 21.50 dB—signifying poor estimation—BKNet attains -10.24 dB, demonstrating robust estimation per-

TABLE VII
BKNET, # OF ADCS VS MSE [DB], HETEROGENEOUS NOISE

$1/a$	1	8	64	128
KalmanNet (ideal observation)	-22.67			
BKNet	-20.83	-26.55	-31.96	-34.05

TABLE VIII
MODEL MISMATCH

	Full	$J = 1$	$\mathbf{f}()$ rotation	$\mathbf{h}()$ rotation
BKF	-17.26	6.24	21.50	-11.66
BKNet	-17.39	-15.19	-10.24	-14.20

formance. Moreover, we anticipate that increasing the number of training iterations or ADC count will further enhance BKNet’s estimation accuracy.

- The final model-mismatch experiment rotates the measurement function by $\theta = 3^\circ$. BKF’s estimation performance remains relatively unaffected with a value of -11.66 dB, showing only a minor decrease from the full knowledge case. In contrast, BKNet achieves -14.20 dB, demonstrating its ability to correct the model mismatch effectively.

Through these experiments, we confirm that BKNet achieves robust estimation performance under incomplete model knowledge. Especially, the result highlights the effectiveness of combining data-driven and classical filtering approaches. Such robustness stems from the structural decomposition into prediction and correction steps as in (49), where the data-driven correction effectively mitigates model uncertainties even under 1-bit observations.

F. Real World Dynamics: Michigan NCLT Dataset

In this subsection, we evaluate the performance of BKF and BKNet using the Michigan NCLT dataset [28], which provides path trajectories from an actual Segway robot. This dataset consists of time-series measurements from various noisy sensors mounted on the robot, including GPS, an odometer, and LiDAR. For this real-time tracking experiment, we restructured the dataset. The state model input sequence consists of the robot’s GPS-derived position coordinates (x, y) , odometry-derived velocities (v_x, v_y) , and accelerations (a_x, a_y) , as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}_\tau = (x, v_x, a_x, y, v_y, a_y)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (62)$$

Then, for each axis, under a Wiener-velocity state model with a sampling interval of $\Delta\tau$, the state function matrix \mathbf{F} and

Fig. 6. State estimation results for the NCLT dataset using 1-bit observations.

process noise covariance \mathbf{Q} can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \Delta\tau & \frac{1}{2}\Delta\tau^2 \\ 0 & 1 & \Delta\tau \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (63)$$

$$\mathbf{Q} = q^2 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{4} \cdot (\Delta\tau)^4 & \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\Delta\tau)^3 & \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\Delta\tau)^2 \\ \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\Delta\tau)^3 & \Delta\tau^2 & \Delta\tau \\ \frac{1}{2} \cdot \Delta\tau^2 & \Delta\tau & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (64)$$

Here, q^2 is the variance of the state model's white Gaussian noise. Since its exact value is unknown, it is set arbitrarily for filtering purposes. The measurement model only provides noise velocity data from an odometer, which means position cannot be directly inferred. Consequently, the measurement function is defined as $\mathbf{H} = (0 \ 1 \ 0)$.

For the NCLT dataset, since the number of features per measurement is fixed at one, all simulations assume only a single 1-bit ADC. Now, considering both the x and y axes, the filtering function can be expressed as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{F} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{F} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{Q} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{Q} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6} \quad (65)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{H} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{H} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 6} \quad \mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} r^2 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & r^2 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}. \quad (66)$$

As with the state model noise, the exact measurement noise variance r^2 is unknown, so it is arbitrarily assigned when applying analytical filtering methods.

We select the trajectory data measured on 2012-01-22 for training. Sampling is performed at 1 Hz and the data are divided into 103 sequences each of length $T = 50$. For testing we select the trajectory data measured on 2012-04-29. In this case, sampling is also performed at 1 Hz and a sequence of length $T = 2000$ is used for testing.

The model functions summarized above are theoretical and their exact values are unknown, so the NCLT experiments represent a case of partial system knowledge. Fig. V-F and Table IX compare the performance of BKF and BKNet on 1-bit observations with EKF and KalmanNet; Table IX also

TABLE IX
THE RESULTS OF NCLT

ideal		1-bit			
EKF	KalmanNet	EKF	KalmanNet	BKF	BKNet
33.41	19.15	37.79	34.67	32.58	18.62

includes the performance of EKF and KalmanNet on ideal observations. EKF and KalmanNet completely fail on 1-bit data because the extreme nonlinearity from quantization violates their fundamental assumptions. BKF's performance also degrades due to its heavy reliance on model accuracy. In contrast, BKNet achieves robust tracking by leveraging DNNs to compensate for incomplete model knowledge.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed novel state estimation methods, i.e., BKF, rBKF, and BKNet, tailored with 1-bit quantized observations. A core idea of the proposed BKF was applying the Bussgang decomposition and dithering to extend the classical Kalman filter to extreme quantization environments. BKF achieved excellent tracking performance, while it required full knowledge of the model and substantial computational overhead to compute time-varying filter gains. rBKF mitigated computational complexity by projecting high-dimensional 1-bit observations into a low-dimensional space. Finally, BKNet employed elaborately designed sequentially connected GRU architecture to learn the Bussgang gain sequence from observed 1-bit signals, so as to overcome the requirement on full system model knowledge. Via the numerical experiments, we demonstrated that the proposed methods achieved excellent state estimation performance, whereas existing methods suffered from severe performance degradation under 1-bit observations. This finding is significant, as it demonstrates that the proposed methods enable reliable state estimation despite the severe distortion introduced by 1-bit quantization, a regime in which conventional approaches typically fail.

Future research can include to modify the BKNet architecture by incorporating physics-informed DNNs, Attention mechanism, or structural priors to enhance generalization under limited data. Designing a more efficient projection operator \mathbf{A} in (41) and extending the framework to few-bit quantization are also promising directions.

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